

READING MATERIALS USING COMIC STRIPS FOR GRADE 1-3 LEARNERS

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Reading Materials Using Comic Strips for Grade 1-3 Learners

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Abstract

This study was purposely conducted to test the effectiveness of comic strips as remediation tool in teaching reading. Specifically it sought to answer: (1) Reading Proficiency Level of Grade 1-3 pupils on Early Grade Reading Assessment (EGRA) pretest and posttest result, (2) the significant difference of Early Grade Reading Assessment (EGRA) pretest and posttest result, (3) the level of acceptability of the comic strips for Grade 1-3 Learners, and (4) the kind of reading material that must be developed based from the result of the study. The research utilized a Quasi-Experimental design wherein the participants were the 117 Grade 1-3 frustration pupils of Dayap Elementary School-Annex based on the Early Grade Reading Assessment (EGRA) pretest. The most important findings of the study are as follows. (1)The Early Grade Reading Assessment (EGRA) posttest result increased by 35.90%. The Reading Proficiency Level of 117 Grade 1-3 Frustration Learners has changed gradually. (2) There were a significant difference in the Early Grade Reading Assessment (EGRA) Pre-test and Early Grade Reading Assessment (EGRA) Post-test. (3) The level of acceptability of the comic strip is highly acceptable. (4) A comic strip can be developed to improve the reading level of the learners.

Keywords: *reading materials, comic strips, frustration pupils, remediation tool, reading proficiency level*

Introduction

All other subjects can be learned using reading as a tool. It gives knowledge about the world and the universe as a whole. We cannot disregard the reality that it also has an impact on the people because it performed a crucial role in the development of the nation. Teachers must therefore take action to encourage reading among students and impart the reading skills required for the grade. (Capin, 2023). Based from Endo's (2022) study, curling up with a favourite book, reading the day's news, or keeping up with the most recent trends in various fields is how some people find joy and unwind during the day. However, for some people, reading is a chore, a terrible assignment to finish, and a task in particular that causes anxiety.

Reading improves focus, memory, empathy, and communication skills, which makes it advantageous. It can shorten lifespans, lessen stress, and enhance mental health. As described by MPL Karen (2020), reading has ten advantages, including exercising the brain, providing entertainment, improving concentration and focus, enhancing literacy, enhancing sleep, enhancing general knowledge, serving as motivation, lowering stress levels, teaching empathy, and increasing general knowledge.

Reading is also a crucial skill that must be mastered because it serves as the basis for learning subjects that span multiple disciplines. However, written comprehension has become significant by way of helping one get employment and admission to several universities. One is in a position to enhance their knowledge base, access new material, explain new information to others, enhance concentration, and reading is a source of entertainment among many other benefits, as stated by Rintaningrum, 2019. In addition, it greatly impacts the betterment of a person's life and academic achievement.

Moreover, reading proficiency is crucial during their student career into adulthood. Numerous studies have demonstrated the serious effects on both the individual student and society as a whole of graduating from school without even the most fundamental reading skills. Failure to read by the third grade is associated with lower achievement levels, a higher risk of dropping out, and a higher risk of involvement with the criminal justice system.

In addition to lowering individual achievement, not being able to read has an impact on the nation's economy and general well-being. Adults with low literacy rates are more likely to be unemployed, have lower earning potential, and have lower success rates (Lara, 2021). The outcomes of the exams for students who took them according to international standards are one of the traditional and alarming issues that draw the attention of the Philippine educational system.

Based from the results of Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study 2003, the percentage of 10-year-old children in the Philippines who are unable to read and comprehend a simple story was estimated to be 69.5% in 2019 (Conoza, 2022). Their poor scores in English, mathematics, and science can all be attributed to the students' deficiency at basic reading and comprehension. Although it improved slightly to 2.66 points, on average, This work sets in within the country's 2022 round of the Programme for the International Student Assessment., according to Senator Gatchalian, the government shall still need to genuinely answer the call to address the education crisis and accelerate learning recovery in the country.

Reading literacy increased to 347 from the initial 340 in 2018, mathematical literacy increased to 355 from 353, and scientific literacy increased to 356 from 357. According to an analysis by the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development of learner level data, increases in reading and math scores of Filipino learners are not statistically significant, as well as the reduction in science scores. Moreover, it has also placed 76th out of the 81 countries in reading, 75th in Mathematics, and 79th in Science. Noting that the change

in scores is not statistically significant, Gatchalian said this implies that despite the outbreak of COVID-19, learners here did not slide backward. Gatchalian further called for the full and effective implementation of reforms initiated in the aftermath of the 2018 PISA round—including Republic Act No. 11713, otherwise known as the Excellence in Teacher Education Act, which purports to upgrade teacher education and training." Another reform is the newly rolled-out MATATAG K-10 Curriculum, which had the original objective of strengthening core skills in literacy and numeracy.

As a result to this, DepEd has crafted D.O. 57, S. 2015 for system assessment, wherein EGRA and EGMA tools shall be used in monitoring and evaluating the implementation of MTB-MLE and literacy and numeracy programs from Kindergarten to Grade 3. This made sure that MTB-MLE was implemented properly. Finally, the Department of Education is stepping up its reading proficiency campaign through the issuance of Deped Order 173, Series of 2019 entitled Hamon: Bawat Bata Bumabasa, 3Bs, as it aims to close literacy gaps among learners. The initiative 3Bs comes out of the needs expressed by learners, drawing on a variety of research and developing effective interventions that will enable students to improve their reading and comprehension grades. It further puts forward the view that together, a student should learn and be in a position to use all six components of reading: oral language, phonological awareness, phonics, vocabulary, fluency, and comprehension.

The DepEd stays firm in its commitment to the provision of quality, relevant, inclusive, and responsive basic education. This further strengthens the current administration's eight-point socio-economic agenda and the MATATAG Education Agenda on the production of informed, job-ready, and active and responsible citizens equipped with critical competencies and skills for life. DepEd launches

D.O. 001, S. 2024 – Implementation of Catch-Up Fridays. Current projects being undertaken by the Department offer opportunities for learners to improve their academic achievement; more specifically, low competence levels in reading based on large-scale assessments at national and international levels. The findings from assessment require urgent attention to address gaps in learning and enhance reading proficiency of these learners. Catch-up Fridays are learning mechanisms that entrench foundational skills, social skills, and other relevant skills needed in realizing the intent of the Curriculum for Basic Education. This is one of the priority activities under the National Reading and Mathematics Programs, each being a core subprogram under the National Learning Recovery Program or NLRP, as provided in D.O. 13, s. 2023.

Additionally, struggling readers are typically defined as students who perform significantly below norms on standardised reading tests and whose low achievement in reading may be caused by a variety of factors, according to Bernardo, A., (2022), and Hall (2005). As a result, they make less of an economic contribution and, if they find themselves without a job, add to state and local governments' unemployment costs. Therefore, addressing reading issues early on in a child's academic career has undeniable long-term benefits for both individuals and society. Similarly, Dudysh (2015) stated that in order for struggling readers to improve, they must be taught specific skills. The importance of intervention programmes and the necessity for teachers to employ clear and concise teaching strategies were also highlighted by the study's findings.

Similarly, Almutari, 2018, asserted that background knowledge problems, fluency problems, vocabulary problems, and reading level problems are all reading problems that adversely affect learners with learning disabilities from comprehending what is read. And to help solve these problems, reading comprehension techniques that have proved successful include the use of graphic organizers, Llego, 2022, questioning, story mapping, peer-assisted strategy, think- aloud exercises, class text discussions, and groupings.

Reading proficiency in the Philippines has been of concern to many educators and policy-makers for quite a long time. In trying to know the cause of this problem, many researches have been conducted, and several interventions have already been initiated to improve students' reading proficiency. With all efforts exerted, reading achievement still lags behind that of most countries in the Philippines. This could be due to various factors, especially the less attention given it gives for reading, which best epitomizes a condition wherein Filipino students are bereft of access to information such as books and other educational materials. (Llego, 2022).

Despite these challenges, some educators and institutions are improving students' reading abilities. The Dayap Elementary School-Annex is not exempted in looking way on how to enhance the reading skills of the students. For instance, the Project RESOLVER (Reading Empowerment in Settling Over from Lower level to a Vital Excellent Readers) intervention programme was started at Dayap Elementary School-Annex. It is one of the school's PPAs (Programmes, Projects, and Activities) and aims to decrease problem readers while ensuring that at least 80% of them advance their reading abilities. It aims to improve students' reading skills, classify students' reading levels using assessments, and cultivate readers' passion. This project will lay the groundwork for some modifications or adjustments for the upcoming academic year and guarantee the calibre of readers it will produce in its students.

Similar to this, Llego (2022), suggested examining intervention techniques that put into place to help students struggling with reading in some way. Strategies include is providing small group instruction, reading program tailored to student's needs, use of graphic organizers to help students understand their reading and identify the main idea.

Past research indicates that comic strips used within the language teaching format significantly raise students' vocabulary, improve students' grammatical competence, boost students' reading skills, and help students who lack writing skills. Aquariza & Susanto, 2023

Comic book is defined by Oxford Learner's Dictionaries as a magazine, normally for children, with a story in pictures according to Encyclopedia Britannica A comic book basically holds bound comic strips, usually in chronological sequence and telling a single story

or a series of different stories.

The comics industry has progressed through several historical stages. Consider the phrase comics. In general, it will be feasible to classify them into branches such as graphic novels and newspapers. Strips, single-panel funny cartoons, superhero comics, web comics, manga, underground comics. According to Bicakci (2018), there are both alternative and western comics.

Research Questions

This study created a Reading Material Using Comic Strips for Grade 1-3 Learners.

1. What is the Reading Proficiency Level of Grade 1-3 Learners based on the EGRA pre-test result?
2. What reading material needs to be developed based on the pre-test result
3. What is the reading proficiency level of Grade 1-3 learners based on the post-test result of the EGRA?
4. What is the acceptability level of the comic strips among Grade1-3 learners?

Methodology

Research Design

This research utilized a Quasi-Experimental Design. Stratton (2019) stated that the In numerous disciplines, including medicine and nursing, health, mental health, and education, pre- and post-test research has been utilized.

It is further discussed that it was a kind of a quasi-experimental study which allowed for the easy evaluation of intervention applied to the test group. The design was appropriate to the study as it utilized an intervention material in the form of Comic strips where performance before and after the utilization of the material was assessed.

Respondents

The respondents of the study will be the Principal, Master Teachers, Grade 1-3 teachers and pupils of Dayap Elementary School-Annex with a total population of 1 principal, 3 Master Teachers, 19 Grade 1-3 teachers and 117 pupil that belongs to frustration level of the Early Grade Reading Assessment (EGRA) pretest from grade 1 to grade 3 who were officially enrolled for the school year 2023-2024.

The study used the purposive sampling technique. Purposeful sampling is a non-randomized method of sampling in which sampling units are handpicked using certain criteria. Sampling for research purposes is a non-probability strategy wherein the researcher chooses the sample, such as persons, cases, or events, based on their judgment that will agree with the objectives of the study.

Instrument

This study utilized an adopted survey questionnaire for the level of acceptability and evaluation of the comic strip reading material from the study of Mr. Romulo Del Mundo Jr. entitled Reading Recovery For Accelerated Literacy Learning Project in teaching Anglo-American Literature and it was standardized and guided by the Division Memorandum No. 122 s. 2017 entitled Submission, Evaluation and Field-testing of Innovative Learning Resources (LRs).The primary data gathering instrument of the study was the standardized Early Grade Reading Assessment (EGRA) tool of Deped pretest and posttest result for Grade 1-3 pupils. The researcher crafted a teacher-made comic strips to serve as an intervention reading material for the frustration pupils to help them improve their reading level. Eventhough the survey questionnaire is standardized the content and context of the instrument was forwarded to the evaluator to identify if the indicators in the instrument was fit in the desired outcome of the study.

The identity of the respondents were confidential in compliance to Republic Act. 10173, otherwise it is referred to as the Data Privacy Act of 2012, which shall protect all forms of information.

Procedure

The researcher asked the permission from Mr. Del Mundo thru e-mail to adopt his criteria for the level of acceptability of the teacher-made comic strips reading intervention material. After obtaining approval, the researcher asked the permission of the school principal to conduct the study to Grade 1-3 teachers and pupils. As the comics strips, reading intervention material being evaluated it was distributed to the teachers and frustrated pupils. It was being implemented within eight (8) weeks covering the third quarter of the school year 2023-2024. After the allotted duration, the researcher ask permission to the Grade 1-3 teachers to conduct the post test of the Early Grade Reading Assessment (EGRA) Then the results was gathered.

Data Analysis

For the analysis and interpretation of the data collected in this study, the following treatment were used:

Frequency count and percentage were used to find out the reading proficiency level of Grade 1-3 learners based on the Pre-test and post-test result.

Paired Sample T-Test was used to test the difference on the pre-test and post-test result.

Mean and Standard Deviation was used to determine the level of acceptability.

Results and Discussion

This section presented the results of the study and the corresponding analysis and interpretation of the data based on the statistical treatment.

Table 1.1. *Grade 1 EGRA Pretest and Post-Test Result*

Proficiency Level	Pre-Test		Post Test	
	F	%	F	%
Independent(91-100)	0	0	0	0
Instructional(61-90)	0	0	14	27
Frustration(1-60)	51	100	37	73
Total	51	100%	51	100%

Data from Table 1.1 showed that there were 51 frustration pupils in Grade 1 during the Early Grade Reading Assessment (EGRA) pretest and 14 pupils moved to instructional level with 27% and 37 among them remained in the frustration level.

As stated by Sampang, R.(2023), the search for an alternate reading solution among struggling readers had been ineffective until reading intervention was performed and analyzed. It had proved of large and positive impact on fluency in reading by learners. This implies that the material (comic strip) used to improved the reading ability of the learners was effective.

Table 1.2. *Grade 2 EGRA Pretest and Post-Test Result*

Proficiency Level	Pre-Test		Post Test	
	F	%	F	%
Independent(91-100)	0	0	0	0
Instructional(61-90)	0	0	12	40
Frustration(1-60)	30	100	18	60
Total	30	100%	30	100%

Data from Table 1.2 showed that there were 30 frustration pupils in Grade 2 during the Early Grade Reading Assessment (EGRA) pretest and 12 pupils moved to instructional level with 40% increased and 18 among them remained in the frustration level.

Golding, S., & Verrier, D. (2021) discussed that evidence reveals that children's ability to grasp information varies, which can lead to miscommunication and have an impact on their future life outcomes. Previous research demonstrates that visual literacy interventions could benefit children who need to process visual information. Comics, which are a highly visual medium, have recently sparked fresh interest in their potential as supportive aids in pedagogical contexts. Visual literacy instruction can help learners understand instructional comics better.

This implies that Grade 2 learners can easily moved to instructional level rather than Grade 1 and Grade 3 learners. They already have the background of the sound of the letter and the recognition of the letter name.

Table 1.3. *Grade 3 EGRA Pretest and Post-Test Result*

Proficiency Level	Pre-Test		Post-Test	
	F	%	F	%
Independent(91-100)	0	0	0	0
Instructional(61-90)	0	0	15	42
Frustration(1-60)	36	100	21	58
Total	36	100%	36	100%

Data from Table 1.3 showed that there were 36 frustration pupils in Grade 3 during the Early Grade Reading Assessment (EGRA) pretest and 15 pupils moved to instructional level with 42% and 21 among them remained in the frustration level.

Based on the study of Osman and Sin (2024), the Use of Comics in Social Studies Education had a huge impact on the teachers' academic and professional experiences. This research determines that comics, as a medium, assisted in professional experience among participants like raising student motivation, having fun while learning, learning for long-term achievements, developing empathy, and habits toward reading.

Table 2.1. *Test of Difference between the EGRA Pretest and Posttest Result Using Comic Strips of Grade 1*

	P-Value	T-Value	Interpretation
Pretest			
Posttest	.000	2.01	Significant

Legend: $P < 0.05$ significant; $P \geq 0.05$ Not Significant

Data from Table 2.1 revealed that there was a significant difference between the pretest performances of the Grade 1 learners in the EGRA Since p- value, the result is significant at p-value =.000 and t-value =2.01.

In line with the study of Anwar S., et. al. 2021, reading helps an individual to grasp, comprehend, understand, and get information. His study was aimed at determining the effect of using photo comics media on reading interest and learning outcomes in elementary social studies subjects. The usage of picture comics medium significantly improves student learning outcomes and reading interest, according to the findings. This was demonstrated when the practice of assigning reading to students changed for the better after they were exposed to picture comics. Furthermore, the integration of photo comic media into classroom activities results in good learning outcomes for students.

Table 2.2. Test of Difference between the EGRA Pretest and Posttest Result Using Comic Strips of Grade 2

	P-Value	T-Value	Interpretation
Pretest			
Posttest	.000	2.05	Significant

Legend: P<0.05 significant; P ≥ 0.05 Not Significant

Data from Table 2.2 stated that there was a significant difference between the pretest performances of the Grade 2 learners in the EGRA Since p-value =.000 and t-value =2.05.

Barnett (2019), in order to address the question of what practices we are engaging in when we think about reading and writing in digital environments—both rendered digital and born digital—Read in Browser: Reading Platforms, Frames, Interfaces, and Infrastructures puts forth the idea that critical infrastructure studies, media archeology, and comparative textual media are all examples of our need for and attempts to account for the qualities of reading and digitalization.

Table 2.3. Test of Difference between the EGRA Pretest and Posttest Result Using Comic Strips of Grade 3

	P-Value	T-Value	Interpretation
Pretest			
Posttest	.000	2.05	Significant

Legend: P<0.05 significant; P ≥ 0.05 Not Significant

Data from Table 2.3 revealed that there was a significant difference between the pretest performances of the Grade 3 learners in the EGRA Since p- value =.000 and t-value =2.05.

According to Wijaya E., et.al.,(2021) past studies have shown that using comic strips in teaching language can help to enrich the vocabulary of students, enhance their grammatical ability, promote reading capacity, and also help students who have weak writing skills. However, these studies have also debated and discussed many limitations about the implementation of comic strips into language teaching, such as appropriacy, themes, and that Comic Strips cannot enhance speaking skills as they can enhance writing skills. It only means that while comic strips could be an effective medium in language teaching, teachers should find ways how to solve the problems that might arise in its implementation.

Table 3.1. Acceptability of the Comic Strips for Grade 1-3 Learners in terms of Description and Rationale

Description and Rationale	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. The description of the IM’s is presented stating its Rationale	3.82	0.39	Highly Acceptable
2. The description of the IM’s is presented stating its Uses	3.86	0.36	Highly Acceptable
3. The description of the IM’s is presented stating its applicability to either individual or group	3.93	0.26	Highly Acceptable
4. The description of the IM’s is presented stating its Levels and abilities of learners	3.89	0.31	Highly Acceptable
5. The description of the IM’s is presented stating its Learning styles	3.79	0.42	Highly Acceptable
Overall	3.86	0.27	Highly Acceptable

Legend: 4.00-3.51 Highly Acceptable; 3.50-2.51 Acceptable; 2.50-1.51 Slightly Acceptable; 1.50-1.00 Not Acceptable

The data from Table 3.1 showed the level of acceptability of the comic strips among KS1 learners based on their description and rationale. The overall mean score was 3.86, with a standard deviation of 0.27. This indicates that the comic strips were very acceptable, as per the verbal interpretation. The indicator with the highest mean (m=3.93, SD=0.26) indicates that the description of the IMs is highly accepted when it states its applicability to either individuals or groups. On the other hand, indicator 5, which describes the IMs' presentation of learning style, has the lowest level of acceptability (m=3.79, SD=0.42).

It is aligned with the study of Enteria (2019) which concludes that comic strip effectively facilitated comprehension by having a clear description and rationale. Furthermore by utilizing the created comic strips, students will gain a better understanding of the concepts presented.

The data implies that there in a high applicability of the comic strip and can be an effective tool in the early childhood education and thereby potentially enhancing engagement and learning.

Table 3.2. *Acceptability of the Comic Strips for Grade 1-3 Learners in terms of Target Audience*

<i>Target Audience</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
1. The Target audience is identified	3.71	0.46	Highly Acceptable
2. The instructional material address diversity of learners and their learning styles.	3.71	0.46	Highly Acceptable
Overall	3.71	0.40	Highly Acceptable

Legend: 4.00-3.51 Highly Acceptable; 3.50-2.51 Acceptable; 2.50-1.51 Slightly Acceptable; 1.50-1.00 Not Acceptable

The data presented in Table 3.2 demonstrated that the comic strips that were created for learners in Grade 1-3 were extremely satisfactory in terms of the acceptance they received from their intended audience. The mean rating for these comic strips was 3.71, and the standard deviation was 0.40. It was determined that the indicators that were discussed with regard to the target audience were extremely satisfactory, with a mean score of 3.71 and a standard deviation of 0.46. According to the findings of the research conducted by Richter, Rendigs, and Mamirina (2019), the utilization of comic strips is evidence that creative and culturally relevant resources are successful in the field of environmental education.

The findings imply the effectiveness of utilizing comic strips as pedagogical aids, underscoring the significance of ingenuity and cultural pertinence in educational resources. These insights can offer valuable guidance for forthcoming scholarly investigations, educational methodologies, and the creation of teaching materials, fostering enhanced and engaging learning environments for young learners.

Table 3.3. *Acceptability of the Comic Strips for Grade 1-3 Learners in terms of Subject Matter, Content and Duration*

<i>Subject Matter, Content and Duration</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
1. The subject matter in which the instructional material is intended for is identified.	3.75	0.44	Highly Acceptable
2. Concept(s) to be taught is/are concretized by using the material.	3.75	0.44	Highly Acceptable
3. The instructional material is challenging and task-oriented.	3.75	0.44	Highly Acceptable
4. Contents are accurate and suitable to the learners' needs and level of development with focus skills and clarify and supplement learner's difficulties	3.89	0.31	Highly Acceptable
5. Desirable values are enhanced, infused and developed	3.79	0.42	Highly Acceptable
6. The duration in the use of the instructional material is indicated	3.68	0.48	Highly Acceptable
Overall	3.77	0.31	Highly Acceptable

Legend: 4.00-3.51 Highly Acceptable; 3.50-2.51 Acceptable; 2.50-1.51 Slightly Acceptable; 1.50-1.00 Not Acceptable

Data from Table 3.3 showed that the acceptability of the Comic Strips for Grade 1-3 Learners in terms of Subject Matter, Content and Duration shows a highly accepted ($m=3.77$, $SD=0.31$). Indicator 4 has the highest mean which indicates that Contents are accurate and suitable to the learners' needs and level of development with focus skills and clarify and supplement learner's difficulties ($m=3.89$, $SD=0.31$) while indicator 6 has the lowest mean wherein the duration in the use of the instructional materials is indicated ($m=3.68$, $SD=0.48$). Likewise, the goal of data comics for data-driven storytelling is to convey data insights through visuals, drawing inspiration from comics' visual language (Bach, et. al 2018).

Furthermore, from the study of Zakaria et. al (2023), the experts came to the unrevised conclusion that the media is legitimate based on factors such as media appeal and language usage. These implies that the materials in comic strip is highly accepted and will lead to positive effect because of following the needs of the subject matter, content and duration.

Table 3.4. *Acceptability of the Comic Strips for Grade 1-3 Learners in terms of Objectives*

<i>Objectives</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
1. The objectives are stated in behavioral terms.	3.82	0.39	Highly Acceptable
2. The objectives focus on teachers on how they could maximize their instructional time.	3.75	0.44	Highly Acceptable
3. The Objectives also focus on learners on how they could understand better the concepts and develop their skills in problem solving and critical thinking.	3.75	0.44	Highly Acceptable
Overall	3.77	0.40	Highly Acceptable

Legend: 4.00-3.51 Highly Acceptable; 3.50-2.51 Acceptable; 2.50-1.51 Slightly Acceptable; 1.50-1.00 Not Acceptable

The acceptability of the comic strips for Garde 1-3 learners in terms of objectives was highly acceptable ($m=3.77$, $SD=0.40$). The objectives are stated in behavioral terms has the highest mean indicator ($m=3.82$, $SD=0.39$) while the objectives focus on teachers on how they could maximize their instructional time, and also focus on learners on how they could understand better the concepts and develop their skills in problem solving and critical thinking also shows highly acceptable result ($m=3.75$, $SD=0.44$).

Moreover, it is also desirable that aspiring teachers display the lesson materials in an engaging and well-presented manner, which is joyful and easy to comprehend, promoting pleasant learning environments (Nispa et. al 2023).

In addition, Utami et. al (2019) from their study cited that When using comic strips as media, the educator should realize that the pupil with this instrument by initially teaching them through comic strips. It will help all the learners to see things from a similar perspective right from the start. Therefore, the teacher should give an elaborate explanation of the comic strips. Before assigning a passage that

presents a similar expose on the kind of text, the instructor should appraise the students' past experience and also know the level of intake by the students. It will help both the teacher and the students to present learning activities. This implies that by knowing and identifying properly the objectives of the comic strips will result to positive effect towards the students.

Table 3.5. Acceptability of the Comic Strips for Grade 1-3 Learners in terms of Outputs

<i>Outputs</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
1. Expected outputs are identified.	3.86	0.45	Highly Acceptable
2. Outputs are useful in developing the concepts taught.	3.93	0.26	Highly Acceptable
3. Outputs are relevant in problem solving and critical thinking.	3.93	0.26	Highly Acceptable
Overall	3.90	0.25	Highly Acceptable

Legend: 4.00-3.51 Highly Acceptable; 3.50-2.51 Acceptable; 2.50-1.51 Slightly Acceptable; 1.50-1.00 Not Acceptable

The data showed in Table 3.5 indicated that the Acceptability of the Comic Strips for Grade 1-3 Learners, in terms of Outputs, was rated as extremely acceptable with a mean score of 3.90 and a standard deviation of 0.25. Indicator 2 and 3 had the greatest mean, indicating that they discuss the usefulness of the outputs in developing taught concepts and their relevance in problem solving and critical thinking (mean = 3.93, standard deviation = 0.25).

Consistent with Utami's (2019) research, the utilization of comic strips has a substantial impact on students' reading comprehension and critical thinking abilities. Moreover, the utilization of narrative text assists students in the development of the concepts presented in the subject matter.

The findings imply the substantial promise of comic strips as an educational instrument, especially in bolstering reading comprehension, analytical thinking, and conceptual growth in young students. The widespread approval and efficacy of comic strips indicate their potential to serve as a valuable asset in contemporary educational methodologies, thereby enhancing the engagement and efficacy of learning processes.

Table 3.6. Acceptability of the Comic Strips for Grade 1-3 Learners in terms of Preparation & Instruction

<i>Preparation & Instruction</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
1. The needed materials are indicated including their quantity and quality.	3.82	0.39	Highly Acceptable
2. Materials to be used by the learners are prepared.	3.89	0.31	Highly Acceptable
3. The Procedure in making the instructional material is orderly presented.	3.89	0.31	Highly Acceptable
4. Instruction for teachers and learners are orderly stated.	3.86	0.36	Highly Acceptable
Overall	3.87	0.25	Highly Acceptable

Legend: 4.00-3.51 Highly Acceptable; 3.50-2.51 Acceptable; 2.50-1.51 Slightly Acceptable; 1.50-1.00 Not Acceptable

Data from Table 3.6 showed that the comic strips were found to be highly acceptable for Grade 1-3 Learners in terms of their effectiveness in preparation and instruction. The educational materials provided for the learners were found to have the greatest mean ($m=3.87$, $SD=0.25$) in terms of their organization and presentation. Furthermore, indication 1 demonstrated a notable level of acceptance, indicating that the required materials, along with their specified quantity and quality, were appropriately identified.

In line with the research conducted by Fauzi et. al. (2023), it is recommended to establish a presenting instrument, such as a projector, prior to adopting the comic strip approach in order to enhance the effectiveness of learning sessions.

The data implies that it becomes evident how comic strips hold substantial promise as efficacious educational instruments, especially when meticulously structured and delivered with suitable technological reinforcement. The discoveries accentuate the significance of comprehensive readiness, superior resources, and the infusion of technology to optimize the advantages of utilizing comic strip-based instruction.

Table 3.7. Acceptability of the Comic Strips for Grade 1-3 Learners in terms of Teaching Hints and Strategies and Assessment and Resource List

<i>Teaching Hints & Strategies</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
Various Hints and Strategies in the use of instructional materials are presented.	3.79	0.42	Highly Acceptable
<i>Assessment and Resource List</i>			
The material provides exercises, drills or activities that allow students to assess their understanding of what they learned and correct their errors.	3.71	0.53	Highly Acceptable
Teachers and learners can monitor learning and use feedback about learners' progress.	3.71	0.46	Highly Acceptable
The material uses authentic assessment.	3.68	0.55	Highly Acceptable
The skills to be assessed are in higher levels of cognitive domain.	3.79	0.42	Highly Acceptable
It is easy to assess students learning.	3.79	0.42	Highly Acceptable
Materials to be used in the activities are prepared.	3.93	0.26	Highly Acceptable
Overall	3.77	0.35	Highly Acceptable

Legend: 4.00-3.51 Highly Acceptable; 3.50-2.51 Acceptable; 2.50-1.51 Slightly Acceptable; 1.50-1.00 Not Acceptable

Data from Table 3.7 shows the acceptability level of the comic strips for Grade 1-3 Learners in terms of Teaching Hints and Strategies and Assessment and Resource List. In terms of teaching Hints and strategies, a mean of 3.79 and SD=0.42 was computed.

In addition, an overall mean of 3.77 and SD=0.35 was computed in terms of Assessment and Resource list. Specifically. Materials to be used in the activities are prepared which indicates a high acceptability ($m= 3.93$, $SD=0.26$) while the materials use authentic assessment has the lowest mean indicator but implies a high acceptability.

Moreover, comics were able to complement strategic strategies such as the school system's standardized curriculum; their appearance and use in classrooms helped to raise teachers' and students' awareness of their usual rhythms. There were consequences for how students and teachers recognized and critiqued literacy practices in their schools. Teachers invited modifications to the environment in which they and their pupils learned by incorporating a comic into their curriculum.(Dallacqua,2020)

Table 3.8. Acceptability of the Comic Strips for Grade 1-3 Learners in terms of Target Audience

<i>Accuracy and Up-to-datedness of information</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
It observes correct punctuation marks and capitalization	3.86	0.36	Highly Acceptable
It observes correct sentence construction.	3.93	0.26	Highly Acceptable
There is no obsolete information and factual and computational error.	3.75	0.44	Highly Acceptable
Overall	3.85	0.31	Highly Acceptable
<i>Design, Layout, & Binding</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
The design, binding and lay out of the material are done creatively	3.96	0.19	Highly Acceptable
Illustrations are adequate, attractive, culturally relevant, properly labeled and realistic with appropriate color.	4.00	0.00	Highly Acceptable
Overall	3.98	0.09	Highly Acceptable

Legend: 4.00-3.51 Highly Acceptable; 3.50-2.51 Acceptable; 2.50-1.51 Slightly Acceptable; 1.50-1.00 Not Acceptable

Data from Table 3.8 revealed that the accuracy and up-to-datedness of information of the comic strips for Grade 1-3 Learners are highly acceptable by the evaluators with overall mean value of 3.85. It was noted that there are correct punctuation marks and capitalization; there are correct sentence construction and all the information are factual. Therefore it implies that context and content is valid. Furthermore, Golding, S., & Verrier, D. (2021), discussed how evidence showed that children differ in their ability to gauge information upon which sometimes misinformation can result to affect life opportunities later on. First, it was shown that visual literacy training could be effective for children who had to process visual information. Comics are a highly visual medium. In addition, lately, there has been a renewed interest in the possibilities of using them as a supportive tool in educational settings. Learners who receive an instruction on visual literacy can understand the instructional comics better.

As Nur (2020) emphasized comics, which draw attention to changing historical conditions, are gaining appeal in both everyday life and education. They can be an effective additional teaching tool for concretizing abstract topics, particularly in science lectures. They can also be utilized to explain abstract concepts to children in an engaging manner. The study's goal was to show that it would comprehend general characteristics, structure, elements, and historical development of comics on the theoretical level.

Conclusions

Conclusions drawn from the presented study are as follows:

Comic Strips Development improved the Reading Level of Grade 1-3 Frustrated learners.

The T-test of difference between the pre-test and post-test result shows significance. Therefore the hypothesis stating that there is no significant difference in the Early Grade Reading Assessment EGRA Pre-test and post-test result was rejected at 0.05 level of significant.

Recommendations are offered based on the findings and conclusions.

Comic strips can be one of the strategies to be used in teaching remedial reading to enhance the students' level of reading.

Endorsement and reproduction of comic strips aligned to competencies may be considered so that other teachers who have frustration pupils may have the chance to use the same intervention reading material.

Follow-up research using comparable design and factors not included in the current study may be undertaken.

Institutionalized the use of comic strip in improving the reading level of frustrated readers.

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